

NEW DESIGN METHODOLOGIES FOR HIGH-SPEED MIXED-MODE CMOS FULL ADDER CIRCUITS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design of high-speed full adder circuits using a new CMOS mixed mode logic family. The objective of this work is to present a new full adder design circuits combined with current mode circuit in one unit to implement a full adder cell. This paper also discusses a high-speed hybrid majority function based 1-bit full adder that uses MOS capacitors (MOSCAP) in its structure with conventional static and dynamic CMOS logic circuit. The static Majority function (bridge) design style enjoys a high degree of regularity and symmetric higher density than the conventional CMOS design style as well as lower power consumption by using bridge transistors. This technique helps in reducing power consumption, propagation delay, and area of digital circuits while maintaining low complexity of mixed-mode logic designs. Dynamic CMOS circuits enjoy area, delay and testability advantages over static CMOS circuits. Simulation results illustrate the superiority of the new designed adder circuits against the reported conventional CMOS, dynamic and majority function adder circuits, in terms of power, delay, power delay product (PDP) and energy delay product (EDP). The design is implemented on UMC 0.18 μ m process models in Cadence Virtuoso Schematic Composer at 1.8 V single ended supply voltage and simulations are carried out on Spectre S.

KEYWORDS

Full adder, Majority-Not gate, Dynamic circuits, MOSCAP, Power-delay product (PDP), Very Large Scale Integrated (VLSI) Circuits, Current mode logic, Hybrid XOR-XNOR circuit, Bridge full adder.

1. INTRODUCTION

Low-power design of VLSI circuits has been identified as a critical technological need in recent years due to high demand for portable consumer electronics products. With the explosive growth in laptops, portable personal communication systems and the evolution of the shrinking technology, the research effort in low-power microelectronics has been intensified and low-power VLSI systems have emerged high in demand. Adder is one of the most important components of a CPU (central processing unit), Arithmetic logic unit (ALU), floating-point unit and address generation unit like cache or memory access unit.

Digital circuit designers have always been encountered in a tradeoff between speed and power consumption to improve their design's performance. There are standard implementations with various logic styles that have been used in the past to design full-adder cells [16-38] and these are used for the comparison in this paper. Although they all have similar function, the way of producing the intermediate nodes and the transistor count are varied. Different logic styles tend to favour one performance aspect at the expense of the others. The logic style used in logic gates basically influences the speed, size, power dissipation, and the wiring complexity of a circuit. The circuit delay is determined by the number of inversion levels, the number of transistors in series, the transistor sizes (i.e. channel widths) and the intra-cell wiring capacitances. The circuit

size depends on the number of transistors, their size and the wiring complexity. Some of them use one logic style for the whole full adder and others use more than one logic style for their implementation.

In addition, full-adders are important components in other applications such as digital signal processing (DSP) architectures and microprocessor. Arithmetic functions such as addition, subtraction, multiplication and division are some examples which use adder as a main building block [1-7]. In nano-scaling, the biggest power consumption is static power dissipation. Depending on the application, the kind of circuit implemented, and the design techniques used, different performance aspects become important, disallowing the formulation of universal rules for optimal logic styles.

There are two types of full adders in case of logic structure. One is static style and the other is dynamic style. Static full adders are commonly more reliable, simpler and of lower power than dynamic ones. Dynamic is an alternative logic style to design a logic function. It has some advantages in comparison with static mode such as faster switching speeds, no static power consumption, non-ratioed logic, full swing voltage levels and less number of transistors. For an N input logic function, it requires $N+2$ transistors versus $2N$ transistors in the standard CMOS logic. The area advantage comes from the fact that the pMOS network of a dynamic CMOS gate consists of only one transistor. This also results in a reduction in the capacitive load at the output node, which is the basis for the high-speed advantage. Dynamic CMOS logic style provides high performance because this logic style is constructed with only high mobility nMOS transistors. Also, due to the absence of the pMOS transistors, the input capacitance is lower. Dynamic full adders suffer from charge sharing, high power due to high switching activity, clock load and complexity. However, dynamic full adders are faster and some times more compact than static full adders. Many researchers have combined these two structures and have proposed hybrid dynamic-static full adders.

Domino CMOS circuits fall under the category of Dynamic CMOS logic, which gives advantage in terms of testability over static CMOS circuits [31]. The inherent problem with Domino CMOS circuit is that it suffers from noise margin problem due to charge redistribution between parasitic capacitances at the internal nodes of the circuit, which may result in false output. Domino is nonratioed logic with faster switching speed and less silicon area required as compared to the full static CMOS logic [3-5]. Domino logic consists of a single clock, which is used to precharge the dynamic node of the circuit in precharge phase and to evaluate the function made by nMOS network in evaluation phase. As technology scaling continues, allowing for more logic gates per chip, complex parallel prefix schemes, and fast adder design become viable. In modern CMOS technologies, transistor sizing has been used to find the optimal trade off between speed and energy consumption of an adder [32].

To summarize, some of the performance criteria are considered in the design and evaluation of adder cells and some are utilized for the ease of design, robustness, silicon area, delay, and power consumption. The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Power consideration in digital CMOS circuits is explained in Section 2. Section 3 explores a review of the full adder design in different logic styles. A review of logic styles with majority functions have been discussed in Section 4. In Section 5, implementations of Majority Function based hybrid full adder methodologies (HyFA1-HyFA5) and mixed mode full adder designs (MixFA1-MixFA3) are discussed. In Section 6 the reported and new majority function based full adder design topologies are simulated and the simulation results analyzed and compared. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. POWER CONSIDERATION IN DIGITAL CMOS

Power is one of the vital resources. Hence, the designers try to save it when designing a system. Power dissipation is dependent on the switching activity, node capacitances (made up of gate, diffusion, and wire capacitances), and control circuit size. There are four source of power dissipation: dynamic switching power due to the charging and discharging of circuit capacitance, leakage current power from reverse biased diodes and sub-threshold conduction, short-circuit current power due to finite signal rise/fall times, and static biasing power found in some logic styles (i.e. pseudo-nMOS).

Dynamic switching power is the major component of overall power dissipation, the low-power design methodology concentrates on minimizing total capacitance, supply voltage, and frequency of transistor. For most CMOS circuit design, the short circuit power dissipation is approximately 5-10% of the total dynamic power. The sub-threshold current is proportional to the transistor device size (W/L) and an exponential function of the supply voltage. Thus, the current may be minimized by reducing the transistor sizes, and by reducing the supply voltage.

Scaling in the supply voltage appears to be the most well-known means to reduce power consumption. However, the lower-supply voltage increases circuit delay and degrades the drivability of cells designed with certain logic style. One of the important obstacles in decreasing the supply voltage is the large transistor count and V_{th} loss problem. By selecting proper (W/L) ratio we can minimize the power dissipation without decreasing the supply voltage.

3. REVIEW OF FULL ADDER TOPOLOGIES

In recent years several variants of different logic styles have been proposed to implement 1-bit adder cells [33-50]. These have investigated different approaches realizing adders using CMOS technology, each having its own pros and cons. There are various issues related to the full adders. Some of them are, power consumption, performance, area, noise immunity, regularity and good driving ability. Voltage mode in a general shape contains two networks. Each of these networks contains transistors which behave like a switch. The pull up network is responsible to produce logical "1" and the pull down network is responsible to produce logical "0". In these circuits, a group of switches is connected and the other group is disconnected in every instant. So we need two groups of switches in constructing these gates, which usually have a contrary operation with each other and is dependent to the output function. The CMOS family gates are good example for comprehension of the structure of these circuits. The logical Boolean expressions between the inputs and outputs are expressed as:

$$\text{Sum} = A.B.C + A.\bar{B}.\bar{C} + \bar{A}.B.\bar{C} + \bar{A}.\bar{B}.C \quad 1$$

$$\text{Carry} = \text{Majority} = A.B.C + A.B.\bar{C} + \bar{A}.B.C + A.\bar{B}.C = A.B + C(A + B) = A.B + B.C + A.C \quad 2$$

Concerns about energy consumption have force digital designers to develop techniques for improving energy efficiency. Many approaches have been proposed for the optimal construction of high-performance VLSI adders in a given technology such as: Proper selection of logic family and prefix, reducing the number of logic stages without increasing gate count, reducing the number of logic gates, reducing switching activity and reducing the wiring complexity [8-15]. The logic circuits are characterized based on the following logic conditions as defined below:

Logic Depth (LD): The maximum number of logic stages from output to inputs. Each logic gate is counted as a stage for fully static implementation. However, in compound designs, the

dynamic gate and the following static gate are counted as one stage. The number of stages depends on the prefix of design. Minimum depth adders are used when high performance is required.

Logic Family Selection: In VLSI design, the selection of logic family is dictated by the system performance target. In structures where the performance target is relaxed or where energy is the primary constraint, static circuits are preferred due to their lower switching activity. In addition to that, static circuits are robust and have become more preferable as technology scales down. However, in high-performance microprocessors, dynamic circuits are often required in order to achieve desired target frequency. There are two types of dynamic circuit families used in modern digital systems: (a) dynamic CMOS domino and (b) CMOS compound domino. The main difference between these families is that CMOS domino utilizes a static inverter at the output, while CMOS compound domino uses a static inverting logic stage. This helps in reducing the power by eliminating power hungry dynamic stages and bundling their functionality in the static CMOS inverting stage. As a summary, static circuits are good for power and domino circuits are good for speed. Compound domino designs can combine the speed advantage of dynamic designs and the power advantage of static designs.

Prefix (p): The number of bits combined at each logic stage as defined above. For example, the two-input dynamic gate and the following two-input static gate is defined as prefix-2 stages for domino designs. The two-input dynamic gate and the following two-input static gate is defined as a prefix-4 stage for compound domino designs. Prefix adders are consisting of two blocks, namely, Sum and Carry blocks. A basic cell in digital computing systems is 1-bit full adder which has 1-bit inputs (A, B, C) and two 1-bit outputs (Sum and Carry).

Prefix Selection: In static CMOS logic, the prefix is mostly limited to 2 because of transistor stack height limitation while dynamic designs enable to use of higher prefixes. As prefix of the design increases the logic depth decreases and it is expected to lead to delay improvement. However, higher prefix requires more complex gates with increased stack height resulting in higher gate delay. Therefore, there is an optimal prefix that depends on the design constraints and implementation.

Load Buffering: Addition of inverters is used to drive the output load because inverters are the most energy-efficient drivers. Extra delays come from the parasitic and effort delay of the added inverters. However, the delay of the original circuit will be reduced since it drives added inverters that are smaller than the output load. In addition, extra energy is consumed by added inverters but the original circuit's size is reduced. There is a tradeoff between the saved delay/energy and extra delay/energy coming from the added inverters. Load buffering provides energy savings for heavily loaded designs under the same delay constraints. As the load is reduced, the energy saving of the adder circuit cannot compensate for the extra energy consumed by the extra inverters. The energy saving of load buffering depends on the driving strength of the original circuit and the path gain.

3.1 Static Full Adder Topologies

Static CMOS logic styles have been used to implement the low-power 1-bit adder cells. In general, they can be broadly divided into two major categories: the Complementary CMOS and the Pass-Transistor logic circuits. The complementary CMOS (C-CMOS) full adder of Figure 1(a) is based on the regular CMOS structure with P type Metal Oxide Semiconductor (pMOS) pull-up and N type Metal Oxide Semiconductor (nMOS) pull-down transistors [3-8]. The series transistors in the output stage form a weak driver. Therefore, additional buffers at the last stage

are required to provide the necessary driving power to the cascaded cells. The advantage of complementary CMOS style is its robustness against voltage scaling and transistor sizing, which are essential to provide reliable operation at low voltage and arbitrary transistor sizes. Moreover, the layout of complementary CMOS circuit is straightforward and area-efficient due to the complementary transistor pairs and smaller number of interconnecting wires. Another adder shown in Figure 1(b) is the *Complementary Pass Transistor Logic (CPL)* with swing restoration, which uses 32 transistors [6-9].

Figure1. Conventional Static full adders

The *Pass-Transistor Logic (PTL)* is a better way to implement circuits designed for low power applications. The low power pass-transistor logic and its design analysis procedures were reported in [18-21]. The advantage is that one pass-transistor network (either pMOS or nMOS) is sufficient to implement the logic function, which results in smaller number of transistors and smaller input load. Moreover, direct V_{DD} -to-ground paths, which may lead to short-circuit energy dissipation, are eliminated. However, pass-transistor logic has an inherent threshold voltage (V_{th}) drop problem. The output is a weak logic “1” when “1” is passed through a nMOS and is a weak logic “0” when “0” is passed through a pMOS. Therefore, output inverters are used to ensure the drivability.

Pseudo NMOS full adder cell operates based on pseudo logic, which is referred to ratioed style. The advantage of pseudo nMOS adder cell is its higher speed (compared to conventional full adder) and less transistor count. The disadvantage of pseudo nMOS cell is the static power consumption of the pull-up transistor as well as the reduced output voltage swing, which makes this adder cell more susceptible to noise. New designed hybrid adder [24] is based on low power transmission gate and pseudo NMOS gate. Transmission gate consists of a PMOS transistor and an NMOS transistor that are connected in parallel way, which is a particular type of pass transistor logic circuit.

Bridge circuits provide a conditional conjunction between two circuit nodes. Since one of the important parameters in circuit design is the chip area, the bridge style might reduce area or increase density of transistors in unit of area. Circuits can be implemented faster and smaller than the conventional as shown in Figure 2(a). Bridge transistors make it possible to create a new path from supply lines to an output through sharing transistors of different paths [37-39]. These transistors are arranged in such a way that validates the correctness of the circuit, and also preserves pull-up and pull-down networks mutually exclusive.

Figure 2(a) Bridge full adder

Figure 2(b) Modified Bridge full adder (24T)

The modified *bridge* (*FA24T*) has 24 transistors shown in Figure 2(b) [39]. In *FA24T* a bridge circuit generates Carry and another bridge circuit is utilized in series with the prior one to generate Sum, while in bridge full adder carry and sum signals are produced in a parallel way. *FA24T* has a better drivability than bridge. The bridge style circuits can be classified into two structures. One of them is fully-symmetric style and another one is semi-symmetric. This classification is based on the similarities amount of P and N networks implementation. If the implementation of P and N is fully-similar then the style of circuit is fully-symmetric, and if those implementations are not similar then we could say it is semi-symmetric. A bridge style enables implementation of CMOS circuits in a symmetric manner which is very useful for VLSI layout design, placement and routing.

There are standard implementations topologies for the full-adder cell design that have been used as the basis of comparison in this paper. The Complementary CMOS full adder (C-CMOS) has 28 transistors and the Complementary pass-transistor logic (CPL) full adder has 32 transistors. The hybrid (26T) full adder is designed in two stages as shown in Figure 1(c). First stage is composed of six transistors to produce the balanced XOR and XNOR function and additional two series pMOS and two series nMOS transistors are used to improve the speed of XOR/XNOR circuit. Second stage is made up of ten transistors and six transistors to create a Carry and Sum output functions respectively. The transmission gate adder (TGA) uses CMOS transmission gate logic [27]. It requires complementary input but features a lower transistor number per stack than in the conventional CMOS full adder. A XOR circuit based Transmission gate full adder (20T) and Transmission function full adder (16T) are designed to improve the circuit performance parameters. Although TGA has few transistors, it has been shown in [27] that extra buffer is needed at each output due to their weak driving capability. A detailed analysis of adder topologies is provided in [27]. Reference [17] has proposed a full adder combining both complementary pass-transistor logic and transmission gate logic. A CPL XOR gate is used to generate the signal $A \oplus B$, and then, transmission-gate logic based circuits are used to generate full-swing Sum and Carry outputs. A CPL-TG full adder has better speed and power dissipation than the conventional CMOS full adder. A low power and high-performance XOR-XNOR based hybrid adder cell called 3T XOR circuit is discussed in ref. [32]. This technique helps in reducing the power consumption, the propagation delay, and the area of digital circuits while maintaining low complexity of full adder logic designs.

3.2. Dynamic Full Adder Topologies

Several variants of Dynamic CMOS logic styles have been used to implement 1-bit full adder cell [33-34]. The main advantages of these logic styles are: high driving capability, low input capacitance and high speed operation due to their characteristics, but the main drawback in these logic styles is power-dissipation due to the higher switching activity than the static logic

designs. There are two phases in dynamic logic. For a structure where output node is connected to V_{DD} by a precharge pMOS transistor, there has to be a pull-down network implemented in nMOS. When Clock=0, circuit enters the precharge phase and when Clock=1, the evaluation phase starts. All the input values should be changed at precharge phase to avoid the charge sharing problem and incorrect functionality. It is because once the output discharges at evaluation phase, there will be no path between output and V_{DD} to charge it again until the next precharge phase. The Sum output function can be described by the following equation:

$$\text{Sum} = \overline{\text{Carry}} \cdot (A + B + C) + A.B.C \tag{3}$$

The NP complementary dynamic CMOS full adder [7] is shown in Figure 3(a). It is based on regular dynamic CMOS designing in two levels with Zipper (NP) technique. The advantage of NP complementary dynamic CMOS style is its performance, but power consumption is high. The reported circuit is to use NP-CMOS (Zipper) logic style to implement the 1-bit full adder cell as shown in Figure 4(a) [34]. In the first stage the $\overline{\text{Carry}}$ function is obtained by using the bridge style [9]. In the second stage the Sum function is gained according to the equation (3). This design has 16 transistors. It has full swing voltage levels. Clock and $\overline{\text{Clock}}$ signals cause both stages of the circuit to enter the evaluation phase simultaneously. The PN complementary dynamic CMOS full adder is shown in Figure 3(c). It is implemented in two level dynamic CMOS logic style with PN technique.

Figure 3-4 Conventional Dynamic full adders

The Multi Output dynamic logic is shown in Figure 4(a) [3]. This design uses one clock signal, which is in contrast to NP and PN complementary designs that use two complementary clock signals, but the speed of this circuit is reduced due to the pMOS transistors used in its design. The other disadvantage of this implementation is that this circuit is not full swing, because discharging the load capacitance of Sum is done through pMOS transistors. Multi-Output dynamic logic design is introduced with the aim of enhancing the previous reported design as shown in Figure 4(b). Two pMOS transistors are used to charge the outputs in precharge phase. The bridge style is used to obtain Carry function and then, Carry itself creates the Sum function. After adding the transistors needed for the inverted inputs to the ones in the design, there will be total 21 transistors.

4. LOGIC STYLES WITH MOSCAP MAJORITY FUNCTION

The Majority function is a logic circuit that performs as a majority vote to determine the output of the circuits [35-36]. This function has only odd numbers of input. Its output is equal to '1' when the number of inputs logic '1' is more than logic '0'. An efficient majority function may be designed by using MOSCAP.

4.1. Majority Not Function

The majority structure is implemented by three input capacitors. These three input capacitors prepare an input voltage that is applied for driving static CMOS inverter. For implementation, the majority not function circuit as shown in Figure 5(a), high threshold voltage (V_{th}) transistors have been used.

Figure 5(a) Implementation of MOSCAP Majority Not Function

The majority gates may be designed with more inputs by this method by increasing the number of input capacitors. The capacitor network is used to provide voltage division for implementing majority logic. When the majority of inputs are '0', the output of capacitor network is considered as logic '0' by the CMOS inverter and consequently the output of inverter is V_{DD} . When the majority of inputs are logic '1', the output of capacitor network is considered logic '1' by the CMOS inverter and consequently the output of inverter is 0V. The input capacitance of the CMOS inverter is negligible and has no effect on operation of the circuit.

4.2. Majority Not Function based Static Logic Gates

Figure 5(b) MOSCAP 10.4f F (NAND, NOR and Majority-NOT) gate

Majority Not function is a logic gate with odd numbers of inputs, and its output is high when the numbers of logic ‘1’s is less than the number of ‘logic 0’s in the input of the logic gate. The Majority not function is implemented efficiently by using only capacitors and a static CMOS inverter. Figure 5(b) shows a circuit used to implement majority-not function with inverter utilizing high- V_{th} for both nMOS and pMOS. This circuit can be used to implement NAND gate using high- V_{th} nMOS and low- V_{th} pMOS, and NOR gate using low- V_{th} nMOS and high- V_{th} pMOS.

4.3. Majority Function based Dynamic Logic Gates

The design of three input Majority Not Function, NAND and NOR dynamic CMOS circuits are shown in Figure 6 [52]. It uses three input capacitances in order to implement different functions with unique circuit implementation. As shown, the number of transistors is reduced leading to lower power dissipation. The three inputs Majority Not Function which is implemented with pre-charge and pre-discharge dynamic CMOS circuit are shown in Figure 6(a) & 6(b). In order to make the pre-discharge circuit working as a Majority Not Function, the threshold voltages of pMOS transistor is reduced to-0.9 V and the values of input capacitances is selected accurately as shown in Figure 6 [52]. This reduction in V_{th} influenced the performance of the circuit, but on the other side the lower power dissipation is gained.

In order to make the circuit shown in Figure 6(c) working as a Majority Not Function, transistor MN1 must be turned on ($V_{gs} > V_{th}$) when at least two out of the three inputs are high, but if the transistor turns on when one of its input goes high, the NOR function is implemented and for implementing NAND function, transistors MN1 must be turned on whenever all the inputs are high. All these function could be designed by selecting the correct values for input capacitances. The values of input capacitances for building majority not Function, NAND and NOR is shown in Figure 6. Simulation results in Table 1 illustrate the comparison of logic gates with MOSCAP based majority function, static and dynamic logic style at 1V [49].

Figure 6. Dynamic CMOS MOSCAP (NAND, NOR and Majority-Not) logic gate

Table 1. Simulation results of NAND, NOR, Majority Not gates in 0.18 μ m at room temp.

Design	Static logic			Majority Function			(Dynamic logic)		
	Delay (ps)	Power (μ w)	PDP (10^{-18} ;j)	Delay (ps)	Power(μ w)	PDP (10^{-18} ;j)	Delay (ps)	Power (μ w)	PDP (10^{-18} ;j)
NAND	36	0.041	1.47	23	0.038	0.87	27	0.051	1.38
NOR	40	0.042	1.68	27	0.039	1.05	26	0.051	1.33
Maj.NOT	43	0.048	2.06	18	0.038	0.68	36	0.049	1.76

4.4. Majority Function based Current Mode Logic

Current Mode Logic (CML) has some advantages over voltage mode MVL. Implementing voltage-mode multiple-valued logic (MVL) requires partitioning the total voltage range, zero to supply voltage in to many discrete levels. Thus, the dynamic range and the noise margin are highly dependent on the supply voltage. In current-mode circuits, currents are usually defined to have logical levels that are integer multiple of a reference current unit. Current can be copied, scaled and algebraically sign-changed with a simple current mirror circuit. The main advantage of current mode comparing to the voltage mode is that the summation in current mode requires no extra elements. Another feature in current mode is that the direction of current can be used to show the sign and as a result the additional bit for representing the sign in numeric system, can be eliminated.

The main feature in current mode circuits is that we can design various logic circuits using threshold detector by changing threshold value and sometimes by increasing or decreasing the number of inputs. The designing of threshold value is possible by changing only the threshold detector transistors dimensions. As can be observed, the uniform structure of current mode circuits, easily allows the designer to increase the number of inputs, while in the voltage mode, this is only possible with increasing the number of transistors. The implementation of majority function in current mode [53-58] with given equation $I_1I_2+I_1I_3+I_2I_3$, is shown in Figure 7. If the sum of the inputs is greater than logic 1.5 (threshold value) then the output current will be equal to reference current else, there is no current at the output.

Figure7. Logic Circuit in Current Mode Majority Function

The threshold function is simply implemented by CMOS inverter. In the circuit illustrated in Figure 7(a), both inputs and outputs are of current in gender. M1 transistor converts quantities of the input currents into voltage and provide it to an inverter. The threshold voltage of the inverter is pointed out with TD and provided to the designer. M2 transistor is switched on and off under the control of the inverter, thus connects and disconnects the output current. Despite of the constant shape of this circuit, it can implement the functions of AND, OR, Majority Function, Majority Not Function and many other functions. If different quantities of TD are specified, the produced functions in the output of this circuit are also changed. As an instance, with a threshold detector from 0.5 OR gate, with the threshold detector from 2.5 AND gate and also with TD from 2 majority function shall be obtained. The circuit in Figure 7(b) is same as the circuit of Figure 7(a) with a difference that in the output which is sinking instead of source.

5. MAJORITY FUNCTION ADDER TOPOLOGIES.

The basic design full adder includes two 3-input NAND and NOR gates with majority not function inputs as shown in Figure 8. As the Table 2 exhibit, Sum is different in merely two places with Majority not function when inputs are 000 or 111. The value of these two functions are not equal at $A=B=C= '0'$ and $A=B=C= '1'$. Therefore, we correct these two states by using a pMOS and an nMOS transistor. These transistors must be arranged in such a way that ensures the correctness of the circuit as shown in Figure 8. Three capacitors are used to generate the \overline{Carry} (majority not function) output.

In six mid-states of the Table 2 the Sum output is equal to \overline{Carry} (majority not function) and the MP1 and MN1 transistors are off. But in all one input state and all zero input state the Sum is obtained by the NAND and NOR gates, respectively. In order to design circuit operations in the given state one nMOS and one pMOS pass transistor are added to the circuit as shown in Figure 5.

Table 2. Truth table for Majority function full adder outputs

Inputs			Full adder output functions					
A	B	C	Carry	\overline{Carry}	Sum	$Sum = Maj(A, B, C, \overline{Carry}, Carry)$	$\overline{Carry} = Maj(A, B, C, Sum, \overline{Sum})$	
0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	
0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	
0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	
0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	
1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	
1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	
1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	
1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	

Figure 8 Basic design methodologies for Majority function based full adder circuit

As discussed before, using a static CMOS inverter and three capacitors, the majority function is attained by replacing NAND and NOR gates with three capacitor and inverter. In view of the fact that three separate capacitors are used for designing each of these gates and that these input capacitors influence the circuit performance by replacing the number of capacitors, the overall performance of the system can be improved. Therefore we have eliminated six out of the nine capacitors.

Figure 9 Majority full adder topologies using 3input MOSCAP with CMOS inverters

The schematic of the majority full adder is based on MOSCAP majority not function with only static CMOS inverter as shown in Figure 9. Simulation results illustrate that the reported adder circuits having low PDP works properly at low voltage [49]. Outputs of the circuit will be connected to power supply or ground and therewith, the circuit has good drive capability. In this design, “a” and “b” inverters implement NOR and NAND functions respectively. These inverter based full adders are a suitable structure for the construction of low-power and high-performance VLSI systems.

The basic idea to generate \overline{Sum} from \overline{Carry} by using 5 inputs majority-not function with three input signals (A,B,C) and with two \overline{Carry} input signals are illustrated in Table 2 [47-48].

$$\overline{Carry} = \overline{Maj(A, B, C)}, \overline{Carry} = \overline{Maj(A, B, C)} \quad 4$$

$$\overline{Sum} = \overline{Maj(A, B, C, \overline{Carry}, \overline{Carry})} \quad 5$$

The majority full adder design is implemented by means of majority function, based on CMOS technology. This design is based on the idea that the carry output function is the same as 3- input majority function shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Basic design approach for Majority Not function based full adder cell

5.1 Reported Majority Function Hybrid and Mixed mode Full Adder Topologies

As reported in HyFA1, hybrid full adder circuit of Figure 11(a) uses 16 transistors. Its output Sum function is based on 5 input majority-not gates. In this design, the first majority-not gate is implemented with a high-performance CMOS bridge circuit [48]. This design uses more transistors, called bridge transistors, sharing transistors of different paths to generate new paths from supply lines to circuit outputs. The bridge design style offers more regularity and higher performance than the other CMOS design styles and is completely symmetric in structure. Using the bridge circuit leads to reduction of delay and power consumption of the full adder cell and it also increases the robustness of the circuit

Figure 11(a) HyFA1 (Majority Bridge)

Figure 11(b) MixFA1 (Current mode Dynamic)

In MixFA1 mixed mode full adder circuit of Figure 11(b) uses 16 transistors. Its output Sum function is based on Current mode majority function. In this design, the first majority-not gate is implemented with a high-performance dynamic CMOS bridge circuit [48]. The advantage of this adder cell is higher speed, lower transistor count and it compromises noise margin.

5.2 Newly Design Hybrid Full Adder Topologies

Figure 12(a) Design 1(HyFA2)

Figure 12(b) Design 2 (HyFA3)

The design1 HyFA2 uses 14 transistors and 3 input capacitors. Full adder output \overline{Carry} function is designed with 3 input Majority Not function logic and output Sum function generated in bridge logic style as shown in Figure 12(a). In this design, the majority-not gate is implemented with a capacitors and high-performance CMOS bridge circuit. The advantage of this adder cell is higher speed, lower transistor count and it compromises noise margin. This type of circuit is preferred in smaller area requirement with lesser delay at low voltage.

The design2 (HyFA3) uses 15 transistors and is based on dynamic CMOS structure. Full adder output \overline{Carry} function is designed with 3 input Majority Not function logic and output Sum function generated in dynamic C-CMOS logic style as shown in Figure 12(b). The advantages of the dynamic CMOS logic style are its robustness against voltage scaling and transistor sizing (high noise margins) and thus reliable operation at low voltages and arbitrary (even minimal) transistor sizes (ratio less logic) are possible. Input signals are connected to transistors gates only, which facilitates the usage and characterization of logic cells.

Figure 13(a) Design 3 (HyFA4)

Figure 13(b) Design 4 (HyFA5)

The design3 HyFA4 uses 16 transistors and is based on regular CMOS structure with pull-up and pull-down transistors. Full adder output \overline{Carry} function is designed in C-CMOS logic style and output Sum function generated from 5 input Majority Not function logic as shown in Figure 13(a). The Pseudo nMOS based Majority-Function full adder design4 (HyFA5) operates on pseudo logic, which is referred to ratioed style. Full adder output \overline{Carry} function is designed in Pseudo logic style and output Sum function generated from 5 input Majority Not function logic as shown in Figure 13(b). This adder circuit uses 12 transistors to realize the negative addition

function. In this circuit all the pMOS are replaced with a single pMOS and its gate is connected to ground terminal. The advantage of this adder cell is higher speed, lower transistor count and it compromises noise margin.

5.3 Newly Design Mixed Mode Full Adder Topologies

In mixed mode designing the majority not function in voltage mode is the matching part of majority function in current mode. In the current mode, the current which is pulled from the \overline{Carry} transistor must be twice as much as the current from input transistors to satisfy the following equations [33]. $Sum = Maj(A, B, C, \overline{Carry}, \overline{Carry})$

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Figure 14(a) Design 5 (MixFA2)

Figure 14(b) Design 6 (MixFA3)

In MixFA2, full adder circuit of Figure 14(a) uses 19 transistors. Its output Sum function is based on current mode majority function. In this design, the first majority-not gate is implemented with a high-performance Static CMOS bridge circuit [35]. In MixFA3 full adder output \overline{Carry} function is designed with 3 input Majority Not function logic and output Sum function generated in current mode majority function logic style as shown in Figure 14(b). In this design, the majority-not gate is implemented with capacitors. The advantage of this adder cell is higher speed, lower transistor count and it compromises noise margin. This type of circuit is preferred in smaller area requirement with lesser delay at low voltage.

6. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation have been performed for different supply voltage ranging from 1V to 1.8V, which allow us to compare the speed degradation and average power dissipation of the reported adder topologies. The results of the designed circuits in this paper are compared with a reported standard CMOS full adder circuits. To compare 1-bit full adder's performance, we have evaluated delay and power dissipation by performing simulation runs on a Cadence environment using 0.18- μm CMOS technology at room temperature. To perform a comparative study of simulation performance of various full adder topologies, the same input test pattern have used 3input signals (A, B, C) and these signals are square waves of equal on and off times.

Each 1-bit full adder has been analyzed in terms of propagation delay, average power dissipation and their products. The values of delay, power, power-delay product and energy delay product of C-CMOS, CPL, Hybrid Majority design full adders are measured. The PDP (10^{-15})j and EDP (10^{-24})sj are a quantitative measure of the efficiency and a compromise

between power dissipation and speed. PDP and EDP are particularly important when low power and high speed operation are needed and its comparison at 1.8V is shown in Figure 16.

For each transition, the delay is measured from 50% of the input voltage swing to 50% of the output voltage swing. The maximum delay is taken as the cell delay. The delays of the newly designed circuits are compared with other reported circuits. Figure 15 shows that the delay of the reported dynamic adders is low as compared with conventional static full adder circuits. Newly designed mixed mode (MixFA2 & MixFA3) adder circuits have very low propagation delay as shown in Figure 16.

Delay (ns) comparison of full adder cells

Power (µW) comparison of full adder cells

Figure 15 Delay & Power comparison of conventional full adder cells

Power, delay, PDP and EDP factors of the designed circuits are simulated at 1.8V for 0.18µm CMOS technology. However, simulation results show that the newly designed circuits can work at other supply voltages and also it is completely robust to voltage variations. The area overhead of the designed circuits is lower than that of reported conventional adders and also than that of some other adder circuits. By optimizing the capacitance parameters and transistor sizes of the full adders that have been considered, it is possible to reduce the delay of all adders without significantly increasing the power consumption, and transistor sizes can be set to achieve minimum *power delay product* (PDP) and *energy delay product* (EDP). All adders are designed with minimum transistor sizes initially and then simulated.

Table 3. Simulation results for delay, power, PDP and EDP of the Majority Hybrid and Current Mixed Mode adder cells at 1.8V V_{DD}

Design	MajFA1	MajFA2	HyFA1	HyFA2	HyFA3	HyFA4	HyFA5	MixFA1	MixFA2	MixFA3
Delay (ns)	0.291	0.162	0.086	0.112	0.057	0.109	0.112	0.013	0.014	0.014
Power (µW)	26.51	55.62	4.40	12.70	14.22	2.91	57.2	231	285	301
PDP (10^{-15})	7.710	9.010	0.380	1.422	0.811	0.317	6.406	3.003	3.93	4.214
EDP (10^{-24})	2.24	1.460	0.033	0.159	0.046	0.035	0.718	0.039	0.054	0.059

Figure16 Delay and EDP of Hybrid and Mixed mode adder cells at 1.8V V_{DD}

6.1. Results and Discussion

6.1.1. Average Power Comparison

In this section, we discuss the effect of supply voltage variation v/s. average power. In our analysis the current mode full adders (MixFA1-MixFA3) are the most power consuming circuit at 1.8V due to constant current source. The power consumption worsens with the increase in the voltage supply. Hybrid full adder HyFA4 has the lowest power consumption in comparison to the other simulated adder circuits. It worked successfully at low voltage supply. The MixFA3 full adder consumes higher power due to use of high power consuming current mode majority function in a single unit.

6.1.2. Delay Comparison

Similar to previous simulation setup, the average propagation delay has been studied with the supply voltage variation in all circuits. Simulation results in Figure 14 show that MajFA1 is the best circuit in terms of speed at 1.8V V_{DD} . It has high delay and high sensitivity against voltage scaling. Design2 HyFA3 is the fastest full adder circuit. MixFA2 keeps a high distance from design MixFA1 and shows better performance than MixFA3. Mixed mode adders have almost the same delay at 1.8V.

6.1.3. Energy delay product (EDP) Comparison

Figure 16 shows the energy delay product of the Hybrid and mixed mode adder circuits. The conditions are same as power and delay simulation setups. In low voltages, designed MixFA1 is better than MixFA2 and new hybrid adders. Table 3 shows HyFA1 and HyFA4 have almost same EDP. All the HyFA4 has better EDP than all new design circuits.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we designed a new class of mixed mode logic family for CMOS technology. An extensive performance analysis of 1-bit MOSCAP based hybrid majority function and current mixed mode function full adders have been presented. Different adder logic styles have been implemented, simulated, analyzed and compared. Using the adder categorization and hybrid-CMOS design style, many full adders can be conceived. As an example, new full adders designed using hybrid-majority function design style with C-CMOS, Bridge and Pseudo logic circuit are presented in this paper that targets minimum delay and EDP. The characteristics of the newly

designed adder circuits are compared against reported designed adders based on the worst case delay, average power dissipation, power-delay product (PDP) and energy delay product (EDP). The comparison of simulation results shows that the performance of the newly mixed mode designs are superior in terms of high-speed as against other reference designs of full adder circuits.

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